

Exploration of the hemocyte surfaceome of *Apis mellifera* by a proteomic and transcriptomic approach

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ABSTRACT

This study maps the surfaceome of *Apis mellifera* hemocytes, the protagonist cells in honey bee cellular immunity. The surfaceome, proteins expressed at the cell surface, is crucial as it determines how cells interact with their microenvironment. Through a combination of proteomic and transcriptomic analyses, 1142 genes encoding cell surface proteins were identified, revealing a high level of diversity. Our analyses identified receptors associated with the major insect immune pathways and proteins previously recognized as hemocyte markers in other invertebrates. Notably, several of the detected genes suggest to encode viral receptors, phagocytosis-related proteins, or proteins involved in hemocyte proliferation. A gene ontology analysis highlighted important functions of the hemocytes. The most prominent cluster was transmembrane receptor protein kinase activity, encompassing over 25 % of the identified terms. Other significant clusters included cell adhesion molecule binding, signalling receptor binding, olfactory receptor activity, and metalloendopeptidase activity. This study suggests several potential honey bee hemocyte markers and establishes a foundation for a novel hemocyte classification based on cell surface markers.

1. Introduction

Honey bees (*A. mellifera*) are essential to global ecosystems and agriculture, mainly for their pollination services. Bee-pollinated crops contribute to approximately one-third of the global human food supply (Khalifa et al., 2021). As food demand rises, concern for honey bee health grows. However, since 1960, honey bee populations have been declining at significant rates across Africa, Europe, and North America (Phiri et al., 2022). This decline is attributed to multiple stressors, including the spread of pathogens and parasites (Smith et al., 2013), pesticide exposure (Tosi et al., 2017), inadequate nutrition (Jones et al., 2021), climate change (Belsky and Joshi, 2019), and habitat loss (Naug, 2009). These stressors not only directly weaken honey bees, but also compromise their immune system, making them more susceptible to infections and environmental challenges. This creates a vicious cycle of decline. Gaining deeper insights into honey bee immune responses is crucial to develop strategies that protect their health and ensure survival.

Honey bees have an immune system divided into two main components: humoral and cellular immunity. The humoral response includes

the synthesis of antimicrobial peptides, the formation of melanin, and the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS). Cellular immunity, on the other hand, relies on hemocytes—immune cells that circulate in the hemolymph (the insect equivalent of blood). These hemocytes perform crucial functions such as phagocytosis, encapsulation, nodulation, and clotting (Lavine and Strand, 2002). Although hemocytes are primarily involved in cellular immunity, they also contribute to humoral immunity. For instance, hemocytes synthesize antimicrobial peptides through the activation of the Toll and Imd signalling pathways, produce ROS and RNS, and generate prophenoloxidase (an enzyme crucial for melanin formation). Different types of hemocytes work together to perform these tasks. However, a consensus on the hemocyte types is lacking. Most researchers agree on the following: 1) prohemocytes: small, round stem cell-like cells that make up a small fraction (<5 %) of the total hemocyte population, 2) plasmatocytes: small, round to spindle-shaped cells that dominate adult hemolymph, 3) granulocytes: larger, round cells containing granules, which are the most abundant in larval hemolymph, 4) oenocytoids: large, round cells likely involved in melanization (Van Steenkiste, 1987; El Mohandes et al., 2010). Gábor (Gábor et al., 2020)

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found that oenocytoids react with an antibody that also binds to granulocytes, suggesting a shared lineage. Other types, such as spherulocytes, adipocytes, coagulocytes, and permeabilized cells, have been mentioned, but their existence remains inconclusive. Physiological differences among honeybee castes—workers (nurses and foragers), drones, and queens— as well as between seasonal phenotypes like summer and winter bees, add another layer of complexity. For example, Hystad (Hystad et al., 2017) demonstrated that phagocytic activity differs among worker castes, with nurse bees showing the highest phagocytic activity compared to foragers and winter bees. Similarly, Marringa (Marringa et al., 2014) reported that hemocyte populations are highly dynamic, with significant variation even among individuals within the same hive.

Comparing the hemocyte systems of insects is challenging. Research on closely related Hymenoptera, including *Bombus terrestris*, *Formicidae* spp., and *Vespidae* spp., is currently limited. In *B. terrestris*, one study reported the presence of prohemocytes, plasmatocytes, granulocytes, spherulocytes, and oenocytoids (Çakıcı et al., 2023). These cell types are similar to those described in *A. mellifera*. Çakıcı's publication, however, follows the general insect hemocyte framework proposed by Lavine & Strand (Lavine and Strand, 2002), and even among closely related species, direct extrapolation is not always possible. For instance, in *Formicidae*, both plasmatocytes and granulocytes are reported as phagocytic cell types (Dourado et al., 2023), whereas in *Vespa orientalis*, plasmatocytes are described as the only phagocytic cell type. In contrast, in *A. mellifera*, phagocytic activity is primarily attributed to granulocytes (Richardson et al., 2018). To examine well-characterized hemocyte systems, it is necessary to turn to model insects such as *Drosophila melanogaster*, *Manduca sexta*, *Galleria mellonella*, mosquitoes, and *Bombyx mori*. In *D. melanogaster*, hemocytes are classified as lamellocytes, crystal cells, primocytes, prohemocytes, and plasmatocytes, with the latter functioning as the primary phagocytic cell type. In mosquitoes, phagocytosis is carried out predominantly by granulocytes, which occur alongside oenocytoids and prohemocytes. Similarly, in Lepidopterans, granulocytes serve as the main phagocytic cells, and the hemocyte repertoire also includes oenocytoids, plasmatocytes, spherule cells, and prohemocytes.

A major obstacle is the morphological similarity between the hemocyte types, which complicates classification and limits understanding of their specific functions. For instance, distinguishing between plasmatocytes and prohemocytes, or oenocytoids and granulocytes, often requires advanced microscopy techniques like interference or phase contrast microscopy (Van Steenkiste, 1987). Due to the limitations of morphological classification, other approaches have been explored to characterize honeybee hemocytes. These include classification based on adherence properties (Negri et al., 2014), lectin binding (de Graaf et al., 2002), functional assays (Richardson et al., 2018), and antibodies targeting intracellular or unknown antigens (Gábor et al., 2017, 2020). However, these methods lack specificity. For example, cells may have similar morphology, adherence properties, lectin binding profiles, and perform the same in functional assays yet differ in their cell surface markers and possibly contribute differently to immune responses. While antibodies targeting intracellular proteins are a promising advancement, they are less ideal for downstream applications due to the need for permeabilization, a process that damages cells.

A non-morphological, objective classification has been achieved for various cell types in different organisms through the use of cell surface markers. Each cell subpopulation is characterized by a unique set of markers, systematically named using the Cluster of Differentiation (CD) terminology. Originally developed for human leukocytes, the CD nomenclature has since been extended to many other cell types and organisms, particularly in laboratory animals and farm animals. These markers are essential for immunophenotyping. In *Drosophila melanogaster*, immunophenotyping based on cell surface antigens has been used to characterize the main hemocyte subpopulations: lamellocytes, crystal cells, and plasmatocytes. Notably, Balog (Balog et al., 2021)

identified an additional hemocyte population expressing a lamellocyte (L4) and a plasmatocyte (P1) marker simultaneously upon immune induction. Similarly, in *Galleria mellonella*, anti-human CD monoclonal antibodies were used for immunoprofiling, resulting in the identification of distinct hemocyte subpopulations expressing these CD markers (Gallorini et al., 2024). Currently, no cell surface marker-based classification exists for honey bees. Developing a marker-based system, similar to the CD system, is valuable because the classification is based on the surfaceome, which defines how cells can functionally interact with their microenvironment. This functional classification is crucial to advance research on honey bee cellular immunity and to understand how stressors impact hemocyte subpopulations.

This research takes the first step towards developing an objective classification of hemocytes by identifying cell surface proteins of *A. mellifera* hemocytes. The surfaceome will be mapped by a proteomic and transcriptomic approach.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Honey bees

In September 2023, honey bees (*A. mellifera carnica*) were collected by removing closed brood frames with ready-to-emerge honey bees from the UGENT apiary (51°1'29"N, 3°42'42"E). These frames were incubated in a temperature chamber at 34 °C until emergence. Honey bees were collected at 24-h intervals. Additionally, brood frames with 8-day-old worker larvae (fifth instar) were removed from the hive and the collected larvae were immediately used for hemolymph extraction. In March 2024 and April 2024, honey bees from the same apiary were collected for the RNA-seq experiment and the adherence experiment respectively.

2.2. Hemolymph collection from adult honey bees

Freshly emerged honey bees were anesthetized by placing them on ice for 30 min. Subsequently, the bees were secured by their thoraces, with the head of the bee towards the fingertips. One pair of wings was removed using tweezers, with a quick pulling motion at the base of the wings (Bogaerts et al., 2009). Hereafter, the thorax was gently squeezed until a droplet of hemolymph emerged (Fig. 1). Hemolymph was only collected when it appeared clear and bees were only held by their thoraces to prevent rupture of the abdominal organs. The droplet was then collected with a micropipette and transferred into a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube (low-protein binding) containing ice-cold Dulbecco's phosphate buffered saline (EDTA-DPBS), pH 7.5 or 100 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer (EDTA-ABC), pH 7.5 each supplemented with 0.02 % EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) at a 1:1 ratio. EDTA was added to prevent melanization and coagulation. Usually, 2–10 µl of hemolymph could be sampled per bee. Hemolymph was pooled to specific volumes depending on the experiment: 80 µl for surface shaving, 200 µl for the adherence assay, and 320 µl for RNA isolation.

2.3. Hemolymph collection from fifth instar larvae

For the collection of larval hemolymph, the method described by Butola (Butolo et al., 2020) was followed. The larvae were held with the head of the larva oriented towards the fingertips. Gentle pressure was applied to extend the head region. Using ophthalmic scissors, an incision in the cuticle corresponding to the head area was made. A micropipette was utilized to collect the exuding hemolymph, which was transferred into a 1.5 mL low-protein binding Eppendorf tube and mixed with ice-cold DPBS or ABC buffer supplemented with 0.02 % EDTA at a 1:1 ratio. Although over 100 µl of hemolymph can be collected from one L5 larva, only 80 µl is taken from each to minimize the risk of contamination.

Fig. 1. Hemolymph collection from an adult honey bee. Clear droplet is the hemolymph.

2.4. Cell surface shaving

Each sample, containing 80 μ l of pooled hemolymph and 80 μ l of buffer, was centrifuged at 0.5G and 4 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 min, after which the supernatant was removed using a filter pipette tip. The pelleted hemocytes were washed at least once with EDTA-DPBS or EDTA-ABC buffer using a 5-min centrifugation step at 0.5G and 4 $^{\circ}$ C. The final hemocyte pellet was resuspended in 15 μ l EDTA-DPBS buffer or EDTA-ABC buffer. Subsequently, the samples were digested with 1 μ g trypsin (Pierce Thermo Scientific) and incubated at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 h. Following incubation, the samples were centrifuged for 5 min at 0.5G and 4 $^{\circ}$ C and the supernatants containing the surface determinants were collected. An additional 16-h peptide digestion was conducted at 37 $^{\circ}$ C using 1 μ g of trypsin, after which the samples were stored at -20° C until LC-MS/MS analysis. In total, 12 samples were analyzed: for each buffer condition (EDTA-DPBS or EDTA-ABC) and developmental stage (adult or larva), three samples were included that had been washed once, twice, or three times.

2.5. Separation of hemocytes based on adherence

A volume of 200 μ l of adult pooled hemolymph was added to a well of a 24-well plate (SPL Life Sciences) containing a sterilized glass coverslip and 300 μ l ice-cold EDTA-DPBS buffer. To allow adherence of the hemocytes, the sample was incubated for 1 h at 27 $^{\circ}$ C. Subsequently, the sample was pipetted up and down repeatedly to detach loosely attached hemocytes from the glass coverslip. The coverslip was then transferred to a new well containing 500 μ l of EDTA-DPBS buffer. The adherent hemocytes were resuspended using a sterilized, nonpyrogenic cell scraper (SPL Life Sciences) by scraping multiple times in different directions. Both the suspension and adherent cells were collected separately into a new 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube and centrifuged for 5 min at 0.5 G and 4 $^{\circ}$ C. The supernatants were discarded and the pellets were washed twice with 500 μ l of EDTA-DPBS buffer. Finally, 1 μ g of trypsin (Pierce Thermo Scientific) was added and the samples were incubated for 1 h at 37 $^{\circ}$ C. After incubation, the samples were centrifuged and the

supernatants containing the surface determinants were stored at -20° C until LC-MS/MS analysis.

2.6. Liquid chromatography – tandem mass spectrometry

Peptides were enriched using Agilent Omix Tips according to the manufacturer's instructions. Peptides were reconstituted in loading solvent A (0.1 % TFA in water/ACN (98:2, v/v)). Approximately 2 μ g of each sample was subjected to LC-MS/MS analysis using an Ultimate 3000 RSLC nano system with ProFlow Technology (Thermo scientific) linked to an Orbitrap Exploris mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) equipped with a Nanospray Flex Ion source (Thermo Scientific) at the VIB-UGent Proteomics Core Facility. The chromatographic separation utilized a trapping phase and a separating column in which peptides were trapped for 2 min at a flow rate of 20 μ l/min in solvent A on a 20 mm trapping column (20 mm trapping column (Thermo Scientific), 300 μ m internal diameter (I.D.), 5 μ m beads) while the sample was loaded on a 25 cm needle packed column made in-house (75 μ m internal diameter (I.D.), 3 μ m beads, C18 Repronil-HD, Dr. Maisch, Germany) mounted in the Ultimate 3000's column oven at 25 $^{\circ}$ C. The elution gradient ranged from 0.5 to 26.4 % MS solvent B (0.1 % FA in water/ACN (2:8, v/v)) for 30 min, followed by a gradient from 26.4 % to 44 % solvent B in 8 min and from 44 % solvent B to 56 % solvent B in 2 min. This elution was first at a flow rate 250 nL/min, followed by a 15-min wash reaching 99 % MS solvent B and re-equilibration with MS solvent A (0.1 % FA in water). The mass spectrometer operated in data-dependent mode - automatically switching between MS and MS/MS acquisition (using minimum intensity threshold = 8000), acquired full-scan MS spectra (350–1200 m/z) and subsequent MS/MS spectra (120–2000 m/z). The former MS spectra were acquired at a resolution of 60,000 in the orbitrap analyser, while the latter MS/MS spectra were acquired at a resolution of 15,000 in the orbitrap analyser. A dynamic exclusion window of 10 ppm was used. Fragmentation occurred at a normalized collision energy of 30 % after filling the trap at a target value of 100,000 cps for maximum 100 ms. The S-lens RF level was set at 70 and precursor ions with single, unassigned and >7 charge states were excluded from fragmentation selection.

2.7. Proteomic data analysis

For data analysis PEAKS Studio (10.6, Bioinformatics Solutions Inc) was used together with the *A. mellifera* (Taxon ID: 7460) database from Uniprot (consulted on September 18, 2023). Trypsin was designated as the digestion enzyme, allowing for a maximum of two missed cleavages and using default identification parameters. Carbamidomethylation of cysteine was set as a fixed modification, while oxidation of methionine and deamidation of asparagine and glutamine were considered as variable modifications, with a maximum of 3 modifications per peptide. Parent mass tolerance was set to 20 ppm, fragment mass tolerance was set to 0.5 Da. Only proteins with $-10\log P > 25$ were considered for further analysis, corresponding to 5 % FDR. The mass spectrometry proteomics data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD067259 and 10.6019/PXD067259.

All identified proteins were evaluated to determine whether they are true cell membrane proteins or incidental intracellular proteins due to lysing cells. Because of the abundance of proteomic data, a script was developed to streamline analysis procedures. This script (see Supplementary Material) was designed to extract accession codes from the proteomic data and cross-reference them with the corresponding FASTA sequences on Uniprot. Based on these protein sequences, deep learning techniques were used, DeepLoc 2.1 (Ødum et al., 2024) and DeepTMHMM (Hallgren et al., 2022), to predict the subcellular location of the protein and its structure. Proteins were selected if at least one transmembrane region and an extracellular domain were predicted by DeepTMHMM, and if DeepLoc predicted the protein to be localized to

the cell membrane.

2.8. RNA isolation

RNA was extracted from hemocytes from 320 μL of pooled hemolymph, equivalent to approximately 5 million hemocytes. The hemolymph was centrifuged at 0.5G for 5 min at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the supernatant was discarded. RNA extraction from the resulting hemocyte pellets was carried out using the Qiagen RNeasy Micro Kit. The pellet was resuspended in 350 μl of RLT lysis buffer supplemented with 1 % β -mercaptoethanol and vortexed. The lysate was then passed through a 20G needle ten times to ensure thorough disruption of the hemocytes. The RNA was purified using the Qiagen RNeasy spin column following the manufacturer's recommendations, including an on-column DNase step. Finally, the RNA was eluted in 14 μL of RNase-free water.

2.9. RNA sequencing

RNA sequencing was performed by BGI Genomics (China) on one adult pooled hemolymph sample and one larvae pooled hemolymph sample. mRNA enrichment was conducted using oligo dT beads to target mRNA molecules with poly A tails. In the next step, mRNA was fragmented into smaller pieces and then converted into first-strand cDNA using random primers. The second-strand cDNA synthesis utilized dUTP. The resulting cDNA underwent end-repair and 3' adenylation, followed by adapter ligation to the 3' adenylation cDNA fragments. PCR amplification was employed for library fragment enrichment, followed by quality control and library circularization steps. Subsequently, the library underwent amplification to generate DNA nanoballs, enabling sequencing on the DNBSEQ platform with paired-end reads of 150 base pairs. BGI also conducted basic bioinformatic analysis, involving the trimming of adaptors and removal of low-quality reads from the raw fastq files. The adult sample generated 24,089,143 clean reads, 7,226,742,900 clean bases, a Q20 of 98.34 %, a Q30 of 93.98 % and a GC content of 37.53 %. The larval sample generated 24,030,382 clean reads, 7,209,114,600 clean bases, a Q20 of 98.32 %, a Q30 of 93.80 % and a GC content of 37.57 %.

2.10. Transcriptomic data analysis

An index was constructed using the reference transcriptome of *A. mellifera* (GCF_003254395.2_Amel_HAV3.1_cds_from_genomic.fna) via the kallisto index command. Transcript abundance was subsequently estimated using Kallisto's pseudo-alignment algorithm through the kallisto quant command. Count files are available through the GEO repository under the following link: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE293998>. Genes encoding membrane proteins were filtered out as described in Section 2.7.

2.11. Gene ontology analysis

Gene ontology analysis was conducted using the ClueGO plug-in for Cytoscape (Bindea et al., 2009). The analysis utilized the Molecular Function ontology dataset (GO_MolecularFunction-EBI-UniProt-GOA-ACAP-ARAP_January 09, 2025). Parameters were configured with a GO level range of 3–15, a minimum of 9 genes per term, and a minimum representation of 2 % of genes. All other settings were maintained at default.

3. Results

3.1. Overview

A total of 1142 genes encoding hemocyte cell surface proteins were identified, with 142 detected through proteomic analyses and 1137 through transcriptomic analyses (Fig. 2). Nearly all of the genes detected

Fig. 2. Venn diagram of the genes encoding hemocyte cell surface proteins identified through proteomic and transcriptomic analyses. A total of 1142 genes encoding hemocyte cell surface proteins were identified, with 142 detected through proteomic analyses and 1137 through transcriptomic analyses.

in the proteomic analysis were also identified in the transcriptomic analysis. Notably, the 142 genes identified through proteomics were among those with the highest expression levels in the transcriptomic data.

Proteomic and transcriptomic analyses were performed on two developmental stages of honey bees: larvae and adults (Fig. 3). In the larval data, 41 genes were uniquely detected. However, their expression levels were generally low (<2 tpm), with the exception of the *uncharacterized gene* LOC409752 (2.55 tpm) and *odorant receptor 13* (2.03 tpm). Similarly, 71 genes were exclusively identified in the adult transcriptomic data, also exhibiting low expression levels (<2 tpm), except for sodium-coupled monocarboxylate transporter 1, which had a tpm value of 6.96.

3.2. Proteomics

Four sample categories were analyzed, representing two developmental stages (larvae and adult) and two buffer conditions (DPBS- and

Fig. 3. Venn diagram of the genes encoding cell surface proteins identified in the different developmental stages. There were 41 genes uniquely detected in the larval data and 71 genes uniquely detected in the adult analyses. However these expression levels were generally low.

ABC buffer) (Fig. 4). Samples prepared in ABC buffer revealed significantly more surface determinants compared to those in DPBS buffer, with 139 and 27 hemocyte surface determinants identified, respectively. The use of DPBS buffer resulted in the identification of only one additional surface determinant. As depicted in the Venn diagram (Fig. 4), seven surface determinants were consistently present in every sample: sodium/potassium-transporting ATPase subunit alpha, solute carrier family 12 member 7, disintegrin and metalloproteinase domain-containing protein meltrin, extended synaptotagmin-1, aminopeptidase, V-type proton ATPase subunit a, and calcium-transporting ATPase. Sodium/potassium-transporting ATPase subunit alpha was found in the hemocytes of shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) and plays a role in regulating ion balance (Tang et al., 2018). Similarly, the solute carrier family 12 functions as an ion electroneutral transporter (Arroyo et al., 2013). These seven proteins are primarily associated with general cellular functions and metabolic processes, making their presence in hemocytes unsurprising.

A total of 45 surface proteins were identified in samples collected from both adherent and non-adherent adult hemocytes (Fig. 5). Of these, 2 were novel hemocyte surface determinants, not previously detected in the non-fractionated hemocyte samples. Notably, only one protein - transmembrane 9 superfamily member - was exclusively present in the adherent fraction, while 17 surface determinants were unique to the non-adherent fraction.

3.3. Transcriptomics

A total of 9571 genes were identified in the transcriptomic analysis of the adult and larval hemocytes (see Supplementary Material Table 2). Genes encoding cell surface proteins were selected based on predictions from DeepLoc and DeepTMHMM models. A total of 1137 genes encoding cell surface proteins were identified through the transcriptomic approach (see Supplementary Material Table 1). The following tables present a selection of genes encoding cell surface proteins of particular interest, including immunity-related genes and genes previously described as potential hemocyte cell surface markers in other invertebrates.

3.3.1. Invertebrate hemocyte cell surface markers

Blood cell surface markers are less well-defined in invertebrates compared to vertebrates, as this remains a relatively novel research area within this animal group. However, differential gene expression (DEG)

Fig. 4. Venn diagram of the surface proteins identified in each sample category.

If the surface protein's presence increases across sample categories, the surface determinant will localize more centrally within the Venn diagram. Proteins exclusively identified in one sample category are situated in the outer corners of the diagram.

Fig. 5. Venn diagram of the surface determinants for the adherent and non-adherent fractions. A total of 45 surface proteins were identified in samples collected from both adherent and non-adherent adult hemocytes. Only 1 protein was unique for the adherent fraction.

studies often suggest higher expression of certain genes in specific hemocyte subtypes. For instance, Hu (Hu et al., 2021) identified several genes linked to either a plasmatocyte-derived cell line or to a granulocyte-derived cell line in the moth species *Ostrinia furnacalis*, many of which were also observed in this analysis (Table 1). Notably, the facilitated trehalose transporter *Tret1*, which was associated with the plasmatocyte-derived cell line in Hu's study, shows high expression in our dataset. Similarly, scavenger receptor class B member 1, sodium channel protein *Nach*, and *prominin-1-A* were also identified. On the other hand, genes such as tyrosine-protein kinase transmembrane receptor *Ror* and toll-like receptor 7, which Hu (Hu et al., 2021) suggested as potential markers for granulocytes, were also detected in this study. Additionally, the scavenger receptor class B member 1 has been shown to play a role in pathogen recognition and antimicrobial peptide synthesis in *Marsupenaeus japonicus* (Bi et al., 2015), and in serving as an opsonin in the clam *Ruditapes philippinarum* (Yang et al., 2019).

In another moth species, *Manduca sexta*, neuroglial-positive plasmatocytes represent a specific subtype of plasmatocytes capable of attaching to foreign substrates. In contrast, neuroglial-negative plasmatocytes could only adhere to other plasmatocytes and granular cells (Nardi et al., 2006). Similarly, in the moth *Mythimna separata*, neuroglial was highly expressed in plasmatocytes (Yokoi et al., 2018).

Ninjurin-2 and *neprilysin-1* are two genes with very high expression in adult *A. mellifera* hemocytes, both of which have been indicated to be present on granulocytes (Grimaldi et al., 2012; Kwon et al., 2021). *Ninjurin-2*, induced by the Toll pathway, may function as a phagocytic receptor and/or plays a role in inducing non-apoptotic cell death (Broderick et al., 2012). *Neprilysin-1* is proposed to act as an immunoregulator in vertebrates and invertebrates (Ottaviani et al., 2012).

The *CD151* antigen has been shown to be highly expressed in granulocytes of shrimp (Sun et al., 2020), while the *CD9* antigen is a specific marker for agranulocytes of the Pacific oyster (Dong et al., 2022). The term "agranulocytes" appears to refer to plasmatocytes, as agranulocytes are described as the smallest hemocytes, characterized by a spherical shape, a large nucleus-to-cytoplasm ratio, and the absence of granules in the cytoplasm. Additionally, genes linked to granulocytes in other invertebrates were identified, such as lysosome-associated membrane glycoprotein 1 (Di et al., 2021), associated with phagocytosis, and dipeptidase 1 (Jiang et al., 2018), which was found in the phagocytic fraction of hemocytes. In contrast, *integrin beta-PS* (Levin et al., 2005) was more prominently expressed in plasmatocytes of *M. sexta*, likely due to its role in spreading and encapsulation.

Table 1

Summary of previously identified hemocyte cell surface markers in invertebrates. For each gene that is a cell surface marker for a specific hemocyte subtype in an invertebrate, the specific hemocyte subtype is given and the reference in which this is stated. The honeybee hemocyte transcriptomic expression levels (tpm: transcripts per million) are reported for each developmental stage (A = adult, L = larva). Detection of the markers in the honeybee hemocyte proteomic analysis is shown per developmental stage (A = adult, L = larva) in two different buffers (a = EDTA-DPBS, b = EDTA-ABC), as well as their presence in the adherent (C) or non-adherent (D) fractions.

Gene name (gene_id)	Hemocyte type	Transcriptomics		Proteomics			
		A	L	A	L	C	D
<i>CD9 antigen (409513)</i>	Agranulocyte (Dong et al., 2022)	50.96	34.67				
<i>ninjurin-2 (725225)</i>	Granulocyte (Broderick et al., 2012; Kwon et al., 2021)	2294.8	237.67	b		x	x
<i>neprilysin-1 (100577845)</i>	Granulocyte (Grimaldi et al., 2012)	1578.27	679.28	a, b	b	x	x
<i>lysosome-associated membrane glycoprotein 1 (409495)</i>	Granulocyte (Di et al., 2021)	961.62	798.02	b	a, b	x	x
<i>CD151 antigen (552124)</i>	Granulocyte (Sun et al., 2020)	514.97	111.82				
<i>tyrosine-protein kinase transmembrane receptor Ror (413616)</i>	Granulocyte-derived cell line (Hu et al., 2021)	6.59	7.35	b	b		
<i>toll-like receptor 7 (410902)</i>	Granulocyte-derived cell line (Hu et al., 2021)	21.51	4.75				
<i>dipeptidase 1 (552636)</i>	Phagocytic hemocytes (Jiang et al., 2018)	8.91	0.46	b	b		x
<i>facilitated trehalose transporter Tret1 (552592)</i>	Plasmatocyte-derived cell line (Hu et al., 2021)	139.6	192.51				
<i>scavenger receptor class B member 1 (100577943)</i>	Plasmatocyte-derived cell line (Hu et al., 2021)	47	67.98				
<i>sodium channel protein Nach (724767)</i>	Plasmatocyte-derived cell line (Hu et al., 2021)	27.39	2.51				
<i>neuroglian (411829)</i>	Plasmatocyte (Nardi et al., 2006; Yokoi et al., 2018)	7.96	4.87	b	a, b		x
<i>prominin-1-A (727302)</i>	Plasmatocyte-derived cell line (Hu et al., 2021)	2.24	1.34				
<i>integrin beta-PS (724950)</i>	Plasmatocyte (Levin et al., 2005)	450.59	326.69	b	b	x	x

3.3.2. Immunity-related genes

As expected, many immunity-related genes were found, since hemocytes are the primary immune cells in *A. mellifera*. The most important immunity pathways in insects - Imd, Toll, JAK/STAT, and JNK - were all represented in the findings (Table 2). The presence of the Imd pathway was confirmed by the detection of *peptidoglycan-recognition protein LC*, which is the receptor necessary for Imd activation (Dziarski and Gupta, 2006). Several toll-like receptors were identified, including

Table 2

Summary of identified genes encoding immunity-related cell surface proteins. Honeybee hemocyte transcriptomic expression levels (tpm: transcripts per million) are reported for each developmental stage (A = Adult, L = Larva). Only Toll-like receptor 4 was found in the proteomic data.

Gene name (gene id)	Function	A	L
<i>TNF receptor superfamily member wengen (726958)</i>	JNK signaling	559.61	500.63
<i>peptidoglycan-recognition protein LC (408924)</i>	Imd pathway	170.89	55.48
<i>croquemort (CD36) (408790)</i>	Phagocytosis bacteria	129.72	50.74
<i>toll-like receptor 4 (724187)</i>	Toll-pathway	84.87	76.15
<i>toll-like receptor 7 (410902)</i>	Toll-pathway	21.51	4.75
<i>TNF superfamily member 12 eiger (725245)</i>	JNK signaling	9.96	2.21
<i>domeless (100576169)</i>	JAK/STAT signaling	4.11	3.7
<i>down syndrome cell adhesion molecule 1 (408786)</i>	Phagocytosis bacteria	3.06	2.64

toll-like receptor 4 (Qiu et al., 2025) and *toll-like receptor 7* (Hu et al., 2021). For the activation of the JNK pathway, *eiger* needs to bind to its receptor *wengen* (Geuking et al., 2005). This analysis showed high expression of the *TNF receptor wengen* in *A. mellifera* hemocytes. Lastly, the *domeless* receptor, essential for JAK/STAT signaling, was detected (Brown et al., 2001).

In addition to these pathways, two important immune genes were identified. *Croquemort* (CD36), which is responsible for the phagocytosis of bacteria and apoptotic cells (Guillou et al., 2016). Secondly, *down syndrome cell adhesion molecule 1*, a hypervariable protein due to alternative splicing, functions in the recognition and engulfment of pathogens (Dong et al., 2006). Both genes can activate downstream signalling pathways.

3.3.3. Other interesting genes

Several additional interesting genes encoding cell surface proteins were identified (Table 3), including *transmembrane 9 superfamily member 4*, *CD63 antigen*, *draper*, and *soritin-related receptor*, all of which are associated with phagocytosis in other invertebrates, such as fruit flies, clams, and crayfish (Bergeret et al., 2008; Shiratsuchi et al., 2012; Yu et al., 2016; Zhu et al., 2022).

Two potential viral receptors, *plasmolipin* and *dyslexia-associated protein*, were identified with relatively high expression levels. These proteins have been shown to localize on the cell membrane and directly interact with viruses in shrimp species *M. japonicus* and *P. monodon* (Matjank et al., 2018; Niu et al., 2022).

Anaplastic lymphoma kinase and *PDGF- and VEGF-receptor-related protein* are both involved in hemocyte proliferation. Zettervall (Zettervall et al., 2004) demonstrated that both proteins significantly increased the number of circulating hemocytes in *Drosophila*. Furthermore, they induced the formation of a specific hemocyte subtype known as lamellocytes.

Additionally, *innexin-2* and *tetraspanin-33* were associated with immune processes in *Scylla paramamosain* and *Haliotis discus discus*, respectively. *Innexin-2* plays a role in hemocyte apoptosis (Wang et al., 2015). Meanwhile, *tetraspanin-33* showed increased expression levels following bacterial stimulation, indicating its involvement in the innate immune system of abalone (Priyathilaka et al., 2017).

Lastly, the soluble *A. mellifera* hemocyte markers (Panyushev et al., 2024) *ferritin 2 light chain homologue* and *hemolactin* were abundantly found in the transcriptomic analysis. In the proteomic analysis both proteins were detected in the samples processed in ABC buffer.

3.3.4. Gene ontology analysis

All adult genes encoding cell surface proteins identified through RNA-seq (1096 genes), were submitted to ClueGO. Among them, 759

Table 3

Summary of other interesting genes encoding cell surface proteins identified in this study. Honeybee hemocyte transcriptomic expression levels (tpm: transcripts per million) are reported for each developmental stage (A = adult, L = larva). Detection of the markers in the proteomic analysis is shown per developmental stage in two different buffers (a = EDTA-DPBS, b = EDTA-ABC), as well as their presence in the adherent (C) or non-adherent (D) fractions.

Gene name (gene id)	Function	Transcriptomics		Proteomics			
		A	L	A	L	C	D
<i>anaplastic lymphoma kinase (408718)</i>	Hemocyte proliferation (Zettervall et al., 2004)	17.47	10.52				
<i>PDGF- and VEGF-receptor related protein (413303)</i>	Hemocyte proliferation (Zettervall et al., 2004)	260.14	138.28	b	b	x	x
<i>innexin inx2 (724832)</i>	Immune response & apoptosis (Wang et al., 2015)	56.39	13.49	b	b		
<i>tetraspanin-33 (725505)</i>	Innate immune response (Priyathilaka et al., 2017)	75.57	57.04				
<i>CD63 antigen (552721)</i>	Phagocytosis (Shiratsuchi et al., 2012)	85.78	46.63				
<i>sortilin-related receptor (408987)</i>	Phagocytosis (Zhu et al., 2022)	46.16	41.81	b	a, b	x	x
<i>transmembrane 9 superfamily member 4 (552723)</i>	Phagocytosis & cell adhesion (Bergeret et al., 2008)	88	115.52	b	b	x	
<i>draper (552479)</i>	Phagocytosis apoptotic cells, bacteria (Yu et al., 2016)	74.17	99.29	b	a, b		
<i>plasmolipin (409019)</i>	Viral receptor (Matjank et al., 2018)	232.82	120.8				
<i>dyslexia-associated protein (411903)</i>	Viral receptor (Niu et al., 2022)	118.61	64.84	b	a, b		
<i>ferritin light chain homologue (551684)</i>	Soluble hemocyte marker (Panyushev et al., 2024)	9140.84	1889.08	b	b	x	x
<i>hemolentin (411597)</i>	Soluble hemocyte marker (Panyushev et al., 2024)	1628.62	931.87	b	a, b	x	x

genes (69.21 %) had functional annotations, and 629 genes (57.39 %) were associated with terms after applying general selection criteria. This analysis resulted in 18 clusters (Fig. 6).

The largest cluster identified is ‘transmembrane receptor protein kinase activity,’ comprising 25,18 % of the identified terms. Kinases are enzymes that transfer phosphate groups, thereby activating or deactivating target proteins. Examples of genes in this cluster include *PDGF- and VEGF-receptor-related protein* and *anaplastic lymphoma kinase*, which are involved in hemocyte proliferation (Zettervall et al., 2004; Parsons and Foley, 2013). Additionally, *tyrosine-protein kinase transmembrane receptor Ror* and *eph receptor tyrosine kinase* were also present in this cluster.

The second largest cluster is labelled ‘monoatomic ion transmembrane transporter activity,’ accounting for 19,42 % of the identified terms. The genes in this cluster are mostly involved in maintaining ion balance, which is essential for volume regulation, and the maintenance of the electrochemical gradient. Examples of genes in this cluster include *sodium/potassium-transporting ATPase subunit alpha*, *copper transporter 1A*, *eag-like K[+] channel*, and *V-type ATPase subunit a family protein Vha100-1*. Additionally, genes like *copper transporter 1A* may also play a role in immune responses, given copper’s antimicrobial properties.

Another cluster identified is ‘ligand-gated monoatomic ion channel activity’ (7,91 %), these genes could potentially play a role in immune signalling. Extracellular ligands can influence the flow of ions into the cell, and these channels can, in turn, regulate processes such as phagocytosis and the production of reactive oxygen species. Within this cluster, 11 genes were linked to neurotransmitter activity. This suggests the presence of a neuroimmune cross-talk. For example, nicotinic acetylcholine receptors and *5-hydroxytryptamine receptor 2A* (a serotonin receptor), both involved in phagocytosis, were identified (Qi et al., 2016; Du et al., 2020).

Next, the ‘metallo-endopeptidase activity’ cluster contains 5,76 % of the identified terms. These genes function by degrading peptide bonds, a process essential for pathogen degradation, detoxification, and the regulation of various signalling pathways through the cleavage of specific proteins. *neprilysin-1*, part of this cluster, acts as an immunoregulator in invertebrates by targeting specific substrates (Ottaviani et al., 2012), while *serine protease nudel* plays a key role in antimicrobial peptide synthesis through the activation of spätzle (Gorman and Paszkewitz, 2001).

A smaller cluster, ‘proton transmembrane transporter activity’ (1,44 %), includes genes with notably high expression levels. These genes are essential to hemocytes for regulating pH levels, which is essential for maintaining homeostasis and facilitating processes like phagocytosis by acidifying intracellular compartments. For example, the *V-type ATPase subunit a family protein Vha100-1* was detected in all proteomic samples and has high expression levels (123,36 transcripts per million), alongside the *vacuolar H + ATP synthase 16 kDa proteolipid subunit*, which has exceptionally high expression (745.07 transcripts per million). Additionally, the *Na[+]/H[+] hydrogen exchanger 1* was identified in this cluster.

Fig. 6. Pie chart representing the most significant Gene Ontology terms (molecular function) of the hemocyte surfaceome. Analysis was performed with ClueGO in Cytoscape.

Almost one percent (0,72 %) of the identified terms were grouped in the cluster 'cell adhesion molecule binding'. This cluster includes genes that play essential roles in migration, tissue infiltration, and cell communication. Examples from this cluster include *neuroglian*, an adhesive protein and plasmatocyte marker in *Manduca sexta* (Nardi et al., 2006); *integrin subunit alpha inflated*, which facilitates hemocyte extravasation in *Drosophila* (Siekhaus et al., 2010); and *E-cadherin shotgun*, an adhesion molecule and marker for stem-like precursor hemocytes in *Drosophila* (Sinenko et al., 2009).

A remarkable observation is the identification of the gene ontology term 'olfactory receptor activity,' representing 0.72 % of the identified terms. A total of 57 genes were linked to this term, with the highest expression observed for the *odorant receptor 13a* gene.

4. Discussion

A broader understanding of honey bee immunity is crucial, given the numerous threats modern honey bees are facing. Hemocytes play a central role in immune responses, making it essential to identify the different hemocyte types. This study explores the hemocyte surfaceome, enabling the identification of potential cell surface markers leading to an objective classification. 1142 genes encoding hemocyte cell surface proteins were identified, indicating great diversity of surface proteins on *A. mellifera* hemocytes. Notably, the 142 genes identified through proteomics were among those with the highest expression levels in the transcriptomic data. This observation suggests that the proteomic analysis may have reduced sensitivity for detecting genes with lower expression levels.

In the LC-MS/MS analysis, the total number of proteins identified in the ABC buffer was significantly higher compared to the DPBS buffer. This increase is likely caused by the detection of more intracellular proteins in the ABC buffer, indicating that it may be causing cell lysis. However, even after excluding intracellular proteins, a tenfold increase in membrane protein identification was observed. This may be due to enhanced protein accessibility for trypsin caused by the lysed cells, facilitating easier identification or by lack of replicates. Another remarkable observation is that the hemocyte surfaceome seems to change with developmental stage. Nine surface determinants detected in larval hemocytes were absent in adult hemocytes, while 21 new determinants appeared in adults. However, the genes encoding these larva-specific proteins were also present in the transcriptomic data for adult hemocytes. This suggests that these proteins are not truly larva-specific but were undetectable in adults due to the lower sensitivity of the proteomic analysis. Additionally, 41 and 71 genes were uniquely found in the larval and adult transcriptomic data, respectively, but at low expression levels. More importantly, the transcriptomic data reveals gene expression levels can differ immensely between adults and larvae. This aligns with previous research by Richardson (Richardson et al., 2018), which showed that certain hemocyte subtypes may be more abundant at specific developmental stages. Moreover, Randolt (Randolt et al., 2008) provided evidence of an immune shift, showing that different antimicrobial peptides are produced in larvae and adult honey bees in response to injury. Similarly, Negri (Negri et al., 2014) found that larval and adult hemocytes differ in appearance and exhibit different attachment and spreading behavior in vitro. These findings support the hypothesis of an immune shift from larvae to adult honey bees.

Fractionating the hemocytes based on adherence to glass was performed to enrich low-abundant proteins and assess potential differences in surface determinants. DPBS buffer was chosen to prevent cell lysis; however, this resulted in a lower number of protein identifications compared to ABC buffer. This reduced the reliability of the data. Nonetheless, this approach facilitated the identification of two additional proteins that were not previously detected in unfractionated hemolymph. The seasonal difference in hemolymph collection might also account for the additional proteins found. The non-fractionated

hemolymph originates from bees collected in September 2023 (probably winter bees), while the fractionated hemolymph was from April 2024 and thus from summer bees. A notable difference in protein numbers was observed between the adherent (28 proteins) and non-adherent (44 proteins) fractions. This disparity could be due to the presence of unstable cells, such as coagulocytes, or increased cell lysis in the non-adherent fraction, which improves protein accessibility for trypsin.

The receptors activating the major immune pathways in insects - Imd, JAK/STAT, JNK, and Toll - were identified. Additionally, several genes of interest were detected, suggesting the presence of immune priming and hemocyte sensing mechanisms similar to those described in *Drosophila*. Notably, *Dscam1* was expressed in *A. mellifera* hemocytes. This gene encodes an adhesion molecule that exhibits hypervariability due to alternative splicing (Schmucker et al., 2000), a feature that, in *L. Vannamei* (Hung et al., 2013) and *A. gambiae* (Dong et al., 2012), contributes to a form of adaptive immunity. These hypervariable isoforms of *Dscam1* may specifically bind pathogens and trigger phagocytosis (Watson et al., 2005). Further research is required to determine whether this occurs in *A. mellifera*. Gene ontology analysis also revealed an unexpected finding: the term "odorant receptor activity." Although this represented a relatively small proportion, its presence was comparable to that of 'cell adhesion molecule binding,' a well-established characteristic of hemocytes, particularly plasmatocytes. While olfactory receptors are typically associated with sensory neurons, hemocytes may use similar receptors to detect environmental cues, such as pathogen-derived molecules or damage-associated signals. The most highly expressed odorant receptor in this analysis was *odorant receptor 13a*, which has been reported to be upregulated in virus-infected bees and in bees subjected to chronic pesticide exposure (Al Nagggar et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2023). The link between immunity and olfactory cues has previously been suggested. Using single-cell RNA sequencing, Kwon (Kwon et al., 2021) identified that hemocyte Clusters 7 and 8 in mosquitoes express genes involved in chemosensory recognition, including odorant receptors. These clusters correspond to immature and mature oenocytoids, respectively. In *Drosophila*, odor perception influences the differentiation of lamellocytes via an indirect pathway: odorant molecules stimulate neurons that release GABA, which subsequently acts on hemocyte progenitor cells (Madhwal et al., 2020). A similar mechanism has been observed in the tsetse fly, where a symbiotic bacterium produces an odorant essential for hematopoietic development in the host (Benoit et al., 2017). The role of odorant receptors in *Apis mellifera* hemocytes remains largely unexplored and needs further research. Potential granulocyte markers may include proteins identified in this study that are already recognized as granulocyte markers in other invertebrates or those associated with phagocytosis, given that granulocytes are considered the primary phagocytic cells in *A. mellifera* hemolymph (Richardson et al., 2018). As all granulocytes were found in the adherent fraction, it was surprising that transmembrane 9 superfamily member 4 was the only protein detected exclusively in this fraction. Other phagocytosis-related proteins, such as the sortilin-related receptor, were present in both fractions. Since plasmatocytes are not typically phagocytic (Gábor et al., 2020), these proteins may serve alternative functions in these cells, or a specific plasmatocyte subtype may participate in phagocytosis.

Additionally, several proteins previously associated with plasmatocytes were identified in the adherence-to-glass experiment: neuroglian (Nardi et al., 2006; Yokoi et al., 2018) and integrin beta-PS (Levin et al., 2005). As both fractions (adherent and non-adherent) contain plasmatocytes, these proteins were expected in both, yet neuroglian, was only found in the non-adherent fraction. This discrepancy suggests the presence of distinct plasmatocyte subpopulations that differ in adherence and surface markers. In *Manduca sexta*, neuroglian-positive plasmatocytes represent a specific subtype of plasmatocytes capable of attaching to foreign substrates. In contrast, neuroglian-negative plasmatocytes could only adhere to other plasmatocytes and granular cells (Nardi et al., 2006). A similar distinction may exist in *A. mellifera*,

making neuroglian a promising candidate marker for a specific plasmatocyte subtype. It is important to note that the previously identified hemocyte cell surface markers may be inaccurate due to species-specific variability. For example, in *Drosophila melanogaster*, plasmatocytes function as the primary phagocytic cells (Melcarne et al., 2019), whereas in honey bees, granulocytes fulfill this role (Richardson et al., 2018). Consequently, while these markers may still hold value, they could correspond to different hemocyte subtypes across species.

While these findings provide valuable insights into hemocyte surface proteins, more data is needed for a complete view of the surfaceome. Factors like season, developmental stage, and health status influence immunity. Future research should explore whether other proteins are expressed in older bees or those facing infections. Another limitation is the uncertainty regarding the types of cells collected. Contaminating cells could be present in the hemolymph due to the rupture of the digestive tract or fat body, though this risk was minimized by using the wing method and only collecting clear hemolymph. Hemolymph was collected by removing the wings and applying gentle pressure to the thorax, which is more robust than the abdomen due to its strong wing muscles. Moreover, the soluble *A. mellifera* hemocyte markers (*ferritin light chain homologue* and *hemolectin*) (Panyushev et al., 2024) were found abundantly, reassuring the identity of the cells collected.

This study represents the first exploration of the *A. mellifera* hemocyte surfaceome, providing a foundation for identifying cell surface markers. This will contribute to a more objective classification of *A. mellifera* hemocytes and may lead to the discovery of new hemocyte subpopulations. The development of monoclonal antibodies against these markers will facilitate future research on honey bee immunity by enabling fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) and flow cytometry-based analyses.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Merel Braeckman: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Lina De Smet:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Bart Devreese:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **Dirk C. de Graaf:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibmb.2025.104398>.

Data availability

The proteomic and transcriptomic data has been made available in the PRIDE and GEO repository respectively.

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